

ON SOME FEATURES OF THE TITRATION CURVES OF CARBONIC ACID AND PHOSPHORIC ACID WITH BARYTA

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Some hitherto unpublished features of potentiometric and conductometric titration curves of carbonic acid and (ortho) phosphoric acid with baryta have been presented and their significance, in the light of the Mass Action principle and the Phase Rule, pointed out. During the titration of carbonic acid, precipitation of BaCO_3 starts from a point where the conductometric titration curve shows a sharp maximum. Precipitation of the carbonate causes an overlapping of the two stages of dissociation and neutralisation of carbonic acid, and only the total quantity of H_2CO_3 is indicated by the titration curve. In the case of phosphoric acid, however, three stages of neutralisation, each culminating in a marked inflexion or break in the titration curve, are clearly indicated for additions of baryta corresponding to the first, the second and the third equivalent of the acid. The monohydrogen phosphate starts getting precipitated when exactly one equivalent of the base has been added. Between the second and the third equivalent of the added base, the p_{H} and the conductivity remain practically constant. It has been shown that this follows from the Phase Rule remembering that, during the addition of the third equivalent, two solid phases, viz., those of the monohydrogen phosphate and the normal phosphate, coexist.

Carbonic acid and phosphoric acid furnish, as is well known, insoluble barium salts. In potentiometric and conductometric titrations of the acids with baryta, these salts will be precipitated when their solubility products are exceeded. Attention has been drawn below to a number of features of the titration curves of the acids with baryta which follow as a direct consequence of the precipitation of the barium salts. No reference to these features could be found in any published work.

EXPERIMENTAL

Saturated solutions of carbon dioxide were prepared by passing purified carbon dioxide through double distilled water, kept in a constant-temperature bath. The (ortho) phosphoric acid used was "Riedel de Haen A.-G." extra pure quality. The saturated solution of barium hydroxide, used for the titrations, was prepared and kept in CO_2 -free atmosphere throughout.

For the potentiometric and conductometric titrations, a fixed volume of the acid solution was taken in each of several pyrex glass bottles to which were then added increasing amounts of the standard alkali solution. After thorough mixing, the bottles were kept, carefully stoppered and sealed (paraffin wax), at a constant temperature in a CO_2 -free atmosphere for 24 hours. The p_{H} and specific conductivity of the contents of different bottles were then determined and titration curves constructed

by plotting them against additions of the base. The p_H was measured with a Beckman p_H -meter (model H-2) and Beckman glass electrodes. For the measurements of the conductivity, a Leeds and Northrup Pt-Ir drum-type bridge, a Muirhead audiofrequency oscillator as the source of alternating current, and Muirhead precision resistances as the known arm of the Wheatstone bridge were used.

DISCUSSION

Fig. 1 shows the potentiometric and conductometric titration curves of water, saturated with carbon dioxide at 24° and 31° .

Each conductometric curve (Fig. 1) shows an initially rising portion and then after passing through a sharp maximum, the curve descends to a pronounced minimum, followed finally by a steeply rising straight portion.

The initial rise in conductivity is evidently due to the formation of barium bicarbonate, $Ba(HCO_3)_2$. The latter dissociates completely giving Ba^{2+} and HCO_3^- ions. At the sharp maximum enough HCO_3^- ions are formed to furnish, by dissociation, an amount of CO_3^{2-} ions, which at the Ba^{2+} -ion concentration obtaining at the sharp maximum, is just sufficient for the solubility product of $BaCO_3$ being reached, as the following calculations will show :

At the sharp maximum, $[Ba^{2+}] = [HCO_3^-] = 1.2 \times 10^{-2}$ g. ions/litre ... (1)

In view of the small value (3×10^{-7}) of the first dissociation constant (K_1) of carbonic acid, the latter affords, by dissociation, only a negligible amount of HCO_3^- ions, and hence, equation (1) gives, to a very fair degree of approximation, the total quantity of HCO_3^- ions in the system at the stage corresponding to the sharp maximum in the conductometric curve.

The concentration of CO_3^{2-} ions at this stage is given by the equation :

$$K_2 = 6 \times 10^{-11} = \frac{[H^+][CO_3^{2-}]}{[HCO_3^-]} = \frac{[CO_3^{2-}]^2}{1.2 \times 10^{-2}} \quad \dots (2)$$

where K_2 is the second dissociation constant of carbonic acid.

From (2), $[CO_3^{2-}]$ at the sharp maximum = 3.48×10^{-7} ... (3),

and from (1) and (3), the ionic product, $[Ba^{2+}][CO_3^{2-}]$, at the maximum = 4.01×10^{-9} , which is equal to or just exceeds the solubility product of $BaCO_3$. Precipitation of $BaCO_3$ should therefore start at the conductometric maximum. This has actually been found to be the case.

As the precipitation of $BaCO_3$ and neutralisation of carbonic acid continue beyond the conductometric maximum, the total ionic concentration of the system

FIG. 1

goes on decreasing till the minimum in the conductometric curve is reached, when both the neutralisation and precipitation reactions are completed. The sharp rise in conductivity beyond the conductivity minimum is evidently due to an increasing accumulation of free $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ in the system.

The amounts of CO_2 at the minima of the two conductometric titration curves are 3.25×10^{-3} and 2.45×10^{-3} moles per litre. The pronounced inflexions in the two p_{H} -titration curves also give the same amounts of CO_2 . Hodgeman (*Handbook of Chemistry & Physics*, 1935, Vol. 20, p. 890) reports 3.3×10^{-3} and 2.6×10^{-3} moles of CO_2 per litre of water, saturated with the gas at 24° and 31° respectively. Agreement between the two sets of values is fairly satisfactory.

Precipitation of BaCO_3 at and beyond the conductometric maximum has a profound influence on the p_{H} -titration curve also. In the titration of H_2CO_3 with NaOH or KOH , neutralisation of H^+ ions, produced by the dissociation of H_2CO_3 into H^+ and HCO_3^- and of HCO_3^- into H^+ and CO_3^{2-} takes place in two distinct steps, and the titration curve shows two regions of buffering and two inflexions (Britton, "Hydrogen Ions", Chapman & Hall, 1942, Part II, p. 172). However, as will be seen from Fig. 1, the titration curve with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ shows only one region of buffering and one inflexion. The two stages of dissociation, represented by the equations, $\text{H}_2\text{CO}_3 = \text{HCO}_3^- + \text{H}^+$; and $\text{HCO}_3^- = \text{CO}_3^{2-} + \text{H}^+$, merge, and the neutralisation of H^+ ions produced in the two stages proceeds as a continuous process, culminating in the one and only inflexion in the p_{H} -titration curve. The cause of this merging is to be sought in the precipitation of BaCO_3 beyond the conductometric maximum and up to the conductometric minimum. Within this range, the HCO_3^- ions, formed as $\text{Ba}(\text{HCO}_3)_2$ following each successive addition of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$, dissociates to provide CO_3^{2-} ions. However, since the solution is already saturated with BaCO_3 , these CO_3^{2-} ions are immediately thrown down as BaCO_3 , and this process continues till the entire amount of HCO_3^- ions formed on the addition of $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ dissociates, producing (i) H^+ ions which are neutralised by the OH^- ions of the base, and (ii) CO_3^{2-} ions, which are precipitated as BaCO_3 . On the whole, therefore, the demands made by the precipitation process are such that the two stages of dissociation,

overlap, and neutralisation of both the H^+ ions proceeds as one continuous process.

Demands of a somewhat different nature on the dissociation and neutralisation of phosphoric acid are made by the precipitation of its insoluble barium salts. This will be seen on a reference to Figs. 2 and 3. Fig. 2 shows the potentiometric and conductometric curves (Nos. 3 and 4) of a 0.02 M solution of H_3PO_4 with 0.295 M- $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$. Titration curves (Nos. 1 and 2) of this acid with KOH are also given in the same figure for comparison. Fig. 3 shows the titration curves of a concentrated solution (0.093 M) of H_3PO_4 with $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$ depicting the final stages of the neutralisation of this acid with the base.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

The p_H -titration curve (No. 1) with KOH, shown in Fig. 2, exhibits, as expected, only two inflexions, indicating a stepwise neutralisation of H^+ ions produced in the first two stages of dissociation :

The end-point of the third stage of neutralisation is, as is well known, masked by hydrolytic effects. The p_H -titration curve (No. 3) with $Ba(OH)_2$, shown in Fig. 2, however, clearly brings out the three steps in the neutralisation of the acid. The curve shows three inflexions, and the acidities at these inflexions are as 1 : 2 : 3, as should be the case. The conductometric titration curve (No. 4) with baryta also shows three distinct changes of curvature corresponding to the three inflexions in the p_H -titration curve.

Beyond the first inflexion in the p_H -titration curve, the monohydrogen phosphate, $BaHPO_4$, is formed and we have found that this salt is precipitated when exactly 1.0 equivalent of $Ba(OH)_2$ is added, that is, immediately following the first inflexion in the titration curve. Britton ("Hydrogen Ions", Chapman and Hall, 1942, Part II, p. 118) found that 1.62 equivalents were required to start precipitation. However, as Britton himself reports, the E. M. F.'s recorded by him during the course of the titration "were not true equilibrium values" but were those measured immediately after each addition of the base. Actually, Britton found that though the precipitation of $BaHPO_4$ started at p_H 6.88 after 1.62 equivalents of base had been added, on standing overnight, further precipitation occurred and the p_H of the solution fell to 6.07. Evidently, the titration curve of phosphoric acid with baryta, reported by Britton (*ibid.*, Part I, p. 193), does not depict equilibrium conditions as sufficient time was not allowed for the processes of neutralisation and precipitation to complete themselves. In our titrations, sufficient time was allowed for the equilibrium to be established and with this precaution, the $BaHPO_4$ was precipitated when exactly 1.0 equivalent of the base had been added, as already mentioned.

Our baryta-titration curve is different from that of Britton in another even more important respect. Britton's curve shows only two inflexions as against the 'three' inflexions observed by us. As noted by Britton himself, the second inflexion in his curve, "occurred during the addition of the third equivalent" of the base, from which he concluded that the precipitate which came down at this stage was a "mixture of di- and tribarium phosphates". Here again, we believe that Britton's failure to record a third inflexion and also the fact that his titration curve showed its second (and final) inflexion much before the third equivalent had been added, are really to be attributed to an incomplete reaction between the reactants as the time allowed for the interaction was not quite sufficient for this purpose. If sufficient time had been allowed for the reactions to complete themselves, a second and a third inflexion would have been observed corresponding to the addition of a second and a third equivalent of the base, as our experience shows.

In our titration, the formation and precipitation of BaHPO_4 are complete at the second inflexion. The reaction with the base beyond the second inflexion is therefore really one between increasing amounts of the added base and a saturated solution of BaHPO_4 which also contains an excess of solid BaHPO_4 . The product of this reaction, $\text{Ba}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, is again another insoluble salt which separates out as a second solid phase as the reaction proceeds.

A striking feature of the reaction between the second and the third inflexion is the fact that both the p_H and the conductivity of the system remain practically constant during this stage. This will be particularly seen from the titration curves in Fig. 3, depicting the course of the third stage of the reaction between a 0.093 M solution of H_2PO_4 and baryta. Both the p_H - and conductivity-curves appear as practically straight horizontal portions during this stage.

Actually, the above features are demanded by and are in harmony with the Phase Rule. As already pointed out, at any stage of the reaction between the second and the third inflexion, the system contains two solid phases, viz., BaHPO_4 and $\text{Ba}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$. These two solid phases and liquid water as well as water vapour, making in all four phases, are in equilibrium. There are three components which may be any three of BaHPO_4 , $\text{Ba}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$, H_2O and $\text{Ba}(\text{OH})_2$. The system is therefore univariant. If now the temperature is maintained constant, as was actually done during the titration, the system loses its only degree of freedom, that is, becomes non-variant, and this is why the composition of the system remains constant during the reaction, as illustrated by the constancy of both the p_H and the conductivity.

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